

Exponential of the Jordan Canonical Form

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1 Introduction

Let us consider the system of linear ODEs (ordinary differential equations), of the first order

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad \dot{X}_{2n,1} = M_{2n}X_{2n,1} + B_{2n,n+1}F_{n+1}$$

with constant coefficients. Cauchy's theorem states that this system – with initial conditions $X(t=0)_{2n,1}$ – has a unique solution. This is given by Lagrange's formula:

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad X(t)_{2n,1} = e^{M_{2n}t}X(t=0)_{2n,1} + \int_0^t e^{M_{2n}(t-\tau)} B_{2n,n+1}F_{n+1}(\tau)d\tau$$

where the initial time is $t=0$, and the exponential of the square matrix is given by

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad e^{M_{2n}t} = \sum_{i=0}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{i!} (M_{2n}t)^i = I_{2n} + M_{2n}t + \frac{M_{2n}^2 t^2}{2!} + \frac{M_{2n}^3 t^3}{3!} + \dots$$

The next paragraphs are meant as a quick summary of some definitions and results in linear algebra that are necessary to remove the exponential of matrix from Eq. 2 and to express the solution in a more meaningful and manageable form (even though the use of the series expansion in Eq. 3 remains always an option). The topics we need to briefly recap are three: diagonalization of a matrix, Jordan canonical form, and exponential of a square matrix.

2 Exponential of a square matrix

This paragraph contains the proofs of some results that will be used in the subsequent paragraphs. It can be skipped and used only as a collection of proofs.

DEF. 1 (*exponential of a matrix*). The function e^{At} , with A – square matrix of dimension n – can be expanded as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad e^{At} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} (At)^i = I_n + At + \frac{A^2 t^2}{2!} + \frac{A^3 t^3}{3!} + \dots$$

PROP. 1 (*first properties*). It can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad e^{A0} = I$$

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad \frac{d(e^{At})}{dt} = Ae^{At}$$

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad A_1 A_2 = A_2 A_1 \Rightarrow e^{(A_1+A_2)t} = e^{A_1 t} e^{A_2 t}$$

DIM. Property in Eq. 5 is obvious. For the derivative with respect to time, by derivation by series we have:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(e^{At}) = \frac{d}{dt} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} (At)^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} \frac{d}{dt} (At)^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} A^i \frac{d}{dt} (t)^i =$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} A^i i t^{i-1} = A \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(i-1)!} A^{(i-1)} t^{(i-1)}$$

If we now make the position $k = i - 1$, we find:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(e^{At}) = A \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} A^k t^k = A e^{At}$$

As for Eq. 7, let us consider that given the hypothesis $A_1 A_2 = A_2 A_1$, it is possible to write a formula that is analogous to Newton's binomial expression:

$$(A_1 + A_2)^i = \sum_{h=0}^i \binom{i}{h} A_1^{i-h} A_2^h$$

To see why this is possible, consider the following example:

$$(A_1 + A_2)^2 = (A_1 + A_2)(A_1 + A_2) = A_1^2 + A_1 A_2 + A_2 A_1 + A_2^2$$

Since $A_1 A_2 = A_2 A_1$, we have $(A_1 + A_2)^2 = A_1^2 + 2A_1 A_2 + A_2^2$, which is the result of the binomial formula for $i = 2$. If we accept that the binomial formula holds for any value of i , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} e^{(A_1+A_2)t} &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\sum_{h=0}^i \binom{i}{h} A_1^{i-h} A_2^h t^i}{i!} \right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{h=0}^i \binom{i}{h} \frac{A_1^{i-h} A_2^h t^i}{i!} \right) = \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{h=0}^i \left(\frac{i!}{h!(i-h)!} \frac{A_1^{i-h} A_2^h t^i}{i!} \right) \right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{h=0}^i \left(\frac{A_1^{i-h} A_2^h t^i}{h!(i-h)!} \right) \right) = \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{h=0}^i \left(\left(\frac{A_1^{i-h} t^{i-h}}{(i-h)!} \right) \left(\frac{A_2^h t^h}{h!} \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

The addends of this series can be obtained by reading Table 1 row by row, from left to right; in other words, it is the series

$$\begin{aligned} I + A_1 t I + I A_2 t + \frac{A_1^2 t^2}{2} I + A_1 t A_2 t + I \frac{A_2^2 t^2}{2} + \frac{A_1^3 t^3}{3!} I + \\ + \frac{A_1^2 t^2}{2} A_2 t + A_1 t \frac{A_2^2 t^2}{2} + I \frac{A_2^3 t^3}{3!} + \frac{A_1^4 t^4}{4!} I + \\ + \frac{A_1^3 t^3}{3!} A_2 t + \frac{A_1^2 t^2}{2} \frac{A_2^2 t^2}{2} + A_1 t \frac{A_2^3 t^3}{3!} + I \frac{A_2^4 t^4}{4!} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

This series is a product series of the two series $\sigma_1 = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{i!} (A_1 t)^i$, $\sigma_2 = \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{h!} (A_2 t)^h$ because its addends are all the possible products $\frac{1}{i!} (A_1 t)^i \frac{1}{h!} (A_2 t)^h$. Since the series σ_1, σ_2 are absolutely convergent, we know that any product series derived from σ_1, σ_2 is absolutely convergent and its sum is the product of the sums of σ_1, σ_2 . In other words, $e^{(A_1+A_2)t} = e^{A_1 t} e^{A_2 t}$ ■

	$h = 0$	$h = 1$	$h = 2$	$h = 3$	$h = 4$...
$i = 0$	I					
$i = 1$	$A_1 t I$	$I A_2 t$				
$i = 2$	$\frac{A_1^2 t^2}{2} I$	$A_1 t A_2 t$	$I \frac{A_2^2 t^2}{2}$			
$i = 3$	$\frac{A_1^3 t^3}{3!} I$	$\frac{A_1^2 t^2}{2} A_2 t$	$A_1 t \frac{A_2^2 t^2}{2}$	$I \frac{A_2^3 t^3}{3!}$		
$i = 4$	$\frac{A_1^4 t^4}{4!} I$	$\frac{A_1^3 t^3}{3!} A_2 t$	$\frac{A_1^2 t^2}{2} \frac{A_2^2 t^2}{2}$	$A_1 t \frac{A_2^3 t^3}{3!}$	$I \frac{A_2^4 t^4}{4!}$...
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots

Table 1. The elements of the product series $\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{h=0}^i \left(\frac{A_1^{i-h} t^{i-h}}{(i-h)!} \right) \left(\frac{A_2^h t^h}{h!} \right) \right)$ can be obtained by reading this table row by row, from left to right.

PROP. 2 (*exponential of similar matrices*). It can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad A = TMT^{-1} \Rightarrow e^{At} = Te^{Mt}T^{-1}$$

DIM. To prove this property, we start proving that

$$(T^{-1}MT)^m = T^{-1}M^m T$$

I proceed by induction, and I start showing that this property holds for $m = 2$. We have:

$$\begin{aligned} (T^{-1}MT)^2 &= (T^{-1}MT)(T^{-1}MT) = T^{-1}M(TT^{-1})MT = T^{-1}MIMT = \\ &= T^{-1}(MI)MT = T^{-1}MMT = T^{-1}(MM)T = T^{-1}M^2T \end{aligned}$$

We now assume true the property for m and show that it holds for $m+1$:

$$\begin{aligned} (T^{-1}MT)^m &= T^{-1}M^m T \Rightarrow (T^{-1}MT)^{m+1} = (T^{-1}MT)T^{-1}M^m T = T^{-1}M(TT^{-1})M^m T = \\ &= T^{-1}(MI)M^m T = T^{-1}MM^m T = T^{-1}(MM^m)T = T^{-1}M^{m+1}T \end{aligned}$$

That said, we can write

$$e^{At} = e^{T^{-1}MTt} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^i (T^{-1}MT)^i}{i!} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^i (T^{-1}M^i T)}{i!} = T^{-1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^i M^i}{i!} \right) T = T^{-1} e^{Mt} T$$

This is what we wanted to prove ■

PROP. 3 (*exponential of a diagonal matrix*). It can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_n \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda_1} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\lambda_2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & e^{\lambda_n} \end{bmatrix} t$$

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad e^{\begin{bmatrix} A_1 & 0 \\ 0 & A_2 \end{bmatrix} t} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} e^{A_1} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{A_2} \end{bmatrix} t}$$

DIM. By applying the series expansion of e^{At} we can write

$$\begin{aligned} e^{At} &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(A^i \frac{t^i}{i!} \right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1^i & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2^i & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_n^i \end{pmatrix} \frac{t^i}{i!} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1^i \frac{t^i}{i!} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2^i \frac{t^i}{i!} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_n^i \frac{t^i}{i!} \end{pmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\lambda_1^i \frac{t^i}{i!} \right) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\lambda_2^i \frac{t^i}{i!} \right) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\lambda_n^i \frac{t^i}{i!} \right) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{\lambda_1 t} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\lambda_2 t} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & e^{\lambda_n t} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

This prove Eq. 9 while Eq. 10 is an immediate consequence ■

PROP. 4 (*exponential of a 2x2 matrix*). It is possible to show that

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad e^{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t \\ -e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix}$$

DIM. We have

$$e^{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix} t} = e^{\left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) t}$$

We note that the product of the two matrices in the exponential is commutative:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha\omega \\ -\alpha\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix}$$

Then we can apply Eq. 7 and we have

$$e^{At} = e^{\left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}\right)t} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix}t} e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\alpha t} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\alpha t} \end{bmatrix} e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}t} = e^{\alpha t} e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}t}$$

The expansion by series of the exponential is

$$e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}t} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}^k t^k}{k!}$$

As for the power of the square matrix we note that – more generally – given a matrix $B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, its powers are

$$\begin{aligned} B^0 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\omega^2 \end{bmatrix}, \\ B^3 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\omega^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega^3 \\ \omega^3 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega^3 \\ \omega^3 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega^4 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega^4 \end{bmatrix}, \\ B^5 &= \begin{bmatrix} \omega^4 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega^4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega^5 \\ -\omega^5 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^6 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega^5 \\ -\omega^5 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^6 & 0 \\ 0 & -\omega^6 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \dots \end{aligned}$$

This leads to the expression

$$B^{2n} = \begin{bmatrix} (-1)^n \omega^{2n} & 0 \\ 0 & (-1)^n \omega^{2n} \end{bmatrix}, \quad B^{2n-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (-1)^{n+1} \omega^{2n-1} \\ (-1)^n \omega^{2n-1} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

When we consider the sum of the powers of B we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^k t^k}{k!} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\omega^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega^3 \\ \omega^3 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \omega^4 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega^4 \end{bmatrix} + \dots = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \left(1 - \frac{\omega^2 t^2}{2!} + \frac{\omega^4 t^4}{4!} \dots\right) & \left(\omega t - \frac{\omega^3 t^3}{3!} + \frac{\omega^5 t^5}{5!} \dots\right) \\ \left(-\omega t + \frac{\omega^3 t^3}{3!} - \frac{\omega^5 t^5}{5!} \dots\right) & \left(1 - \frac{\omega^2 t^2}{2!} + \frac{\omega^4 t^4}{4!} \dots\right) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

If we now consider the well known series expansion of the trigonometric functions

$$\sin t = t - \frac{t^3}{3!} + \frac{t^5}{5!} \dots, \quad \cos t = 1 - \frac{t^2}{2!} + \frac{t^4}{4!} \dots$$

we can conclude $e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix}t} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \omega t & \sin \omega t \\ -\sin \omega t & \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix}$ ■

PROP. 5 (exponential of the Jordan canonical form). It can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda t} & te^{\lambda t} & t^2 e^{\lambda t} & \dots & t^{(n-1)} e^{\lambda t} \\ 0 & e^{\lambda t} & te^{\lambda t} & \dots & t^{(n-2)} e^{\lambda t} \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\lambda t} & \dots & t^{(n-3)} e^{\lambda t} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & e^{\lambda t} \end{bmatrix}$$

DIM. For the sake of simplicity, let us consider a block 3 by 3. We have

$$e^{J_1 t} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda t & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda t & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda t \end{bmatrix}} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} t} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t$$

We then verify that the product between the two matrices in the exponent is commutative:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

It is in fact commutative and this means that we can apply Eq. 7:

$$e^J = e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} t} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t = e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} t} e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\lambda t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\lambda t} \end{bmatrix} e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t}$$

We now note that the non-diagonal matrix has the third power equal to zero:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This means that its exponential can be written:

$$e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t} = I + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^2 \frac{t^2}{2} =$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & t^2/2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & t & t^2/2 \\ 0 & 1 & t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Then we can write

$$e^J = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\lambda t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\lambda t} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & t & t^2/2 \\ 0 & 1 & t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda t} & te^{\lambda t} & t^2e^{\lambda t} \\ 0 & e^{\lambda t} & te^{\lambda t} \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\lambda t} \end{bmatrix}$$

This result can be applied to any block of the Jordan canonical form ■

PROP. 6 (*exponential of the Jordan canonical form*). Given $\lambda = \alpha + i\omega$, it can be shown that

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad e^{\begin{bmatrix} C & I & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & C & I & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & C \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{Ct} & te^{Ct} & t^2e^{Ct} & \dots & t^{(n-1)}e^{Ct} \\ 0 & e^{Ct} & te^{Ct} & \dots & t^{(n-2)}e^{Ct} \\ 0 & 0 & e^{Ct} & \dots & t^{(n-3)}e^{Ct} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & e^{Ct} \end{bmatrix}$$

with

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix}, \quad I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad e^{Ct} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t \\ -e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix}, \quad O = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

DIM. For the sake of simplicity, let us consider a block 3 by 3. We have

$$e^{J_1 t} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} C & I & O \\ 0 & C & I \\ 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} t} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} C & O & O \\ 0 & C & O \\ 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} t} + \begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} t$$

We then verify that the product between the two matrices in the exponent is commutative:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C & O & O \\ 0 & C & O \\ 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} O & C & O \\ 0 & O & C \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C & O & O \\ 0 & C & O \\ 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} O & C & O \\ 0 & O & C \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix}$$

Remember that when matrices are represented by blocks, we can apply to blocks the same rules we apply to elements, when multiplication is performed. Since the product is commutative, we can apply Eq. 7:

$$e^J = e^{\begin{bmatrix} C & O & O \\ 0 & C & O \\ 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} t} + \begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} t = e^{\begin{bmatrix} C & O & O \\ 0 & C & O \\ 0 & 0 & C \end{bmatrix} t} e^{\begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{Ct} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{Ct} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{Ct} \end{bmatrix} e^{\begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} t}$$

We now have

$$e^{\begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} O & I & O \\ 0 & O & I \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} t + \begin{bmatrix} O & O & I \\ 0 & O & O \\ 0 & 0 & O \end{bmatrix} \frac{t^2}{2} = \begin{bmatrix} I & It & I \frac{t^2}{2} \\ 0 & I & It \\ 0 & 0 & I \end{bmatrix}$$

because

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

Therefore, we can write

$$e^{Jt} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{Ct} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{Ct} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{Ct} \end{bmatrix} e^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}t} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{Ct} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{Ct} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{Ct} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & It & I\frac{t^2}{2} \\ 0 & I & It \\ 0 & 0 & I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{Ct} & e^{Ct}t & e^{Ct}t^2 \\ 0 & e^{Ct} & e^{Ct}t \\ 0 & 0 & e^{Ct} \end{bmatrix}$$

where – for PROP. 4 – we have

$$e^{Ct} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t \\ -e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix}$$

And the proposition is proven ■

3 Case of unique eigenvalues

DEF. 2 (*eigenvalues, eigenvectors*). Given a linear function $F: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ (*endomorphism*), we say that $\hat{v} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is an eigenvector of F when there is a scalar λ such that $F(\hat{v}) = \lambda\hat{v}$. The scalar is called eigenvalue of F with respect to \hat{v} .

DEF. 3 (*characteristic equation*). Let us say that A is the matrix of F with respect to base B . In other words: $F(\hat{v}) = BAX$, with $\hat{v} = BX$. Then the relationship between an eigenvector \hat{v} and its eigenvalue is:

$$BAX = \lambda BX \Leftrightarrow AX = \lambda X \Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda I)X = 0$$

In order for this homogenous linear system to have more than the trivial solution, the determinant of its matrix $A - \lambda I$ must be zero. This leads to the condition $\det(A - \lambda I) = 0$, which is an algebraic equation in λ , whose order is the dimension of A . This equation is called the characteristic equation of F .

DEF. 4 (*algebraic multiplicity*). If the characteristic equation has a solution λ repeated r times, we say the algebraic multiplicity of λ is r .

DEF. 5 (*geometric multiplicity*). The dimension of the eigenspace associated to a given eigenvalue is called geometric multiplicity of the eigenvalue. The geometric multiplicity cannot be greater than the algebraic multiplicity.

PROP. 7 (*multiplicity*). The algebraic multiplicity of an eigenvector is always equal or greater than its geometric multiplicity.

DIM. Omitted ■

PROP. 8 (*diagonalization*). If the eigenvalues of F are all different (either real or complex and conjugate), then the set of eigenvectors constitute a base of \mathbb{R}^n and it is possible to write $A = P\Delta P^{-1}$ where P is a matrix whose columns are the coordinates of the eigenvectors of A and where Δ is a diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements are the eigenvalues of A .

Eigenvalues and eigenvector must be placed in the same order (see the following examples). Note that if the solutions of the characteristic equation are not all different, this results is not necessarily true. This case will be dealt with later. More generally, this result applies also in the case of algebraic multiplicity above one, when the corresponding geometric multiplicity has the same value, for all the eigenvalues.

DIM. Omitted ■

PROP. 9 (*change of coordinates*). If we introduce the new base $B' = BP^{-1}$, the matrix of the endomorphism F with respect to B' is given by $A' = PAP^{-1}$, where A is the matrix of the endomorphism with respect to B . Eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the endomorphism remain the same.

DIM. We can write

$$\begin{aligned} F(\hat{v}) &= B(AX) = B'P(AX) = B'P(AP^{-1}X') = B'(PAP^{-1})X' \\ \hat{v} &= BX = B'PX = B'X' \Rightarrow X = P^{-1}X' \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the new matrix of the endomorphism is PAP^{-1} . As for the eigenvalues we have

$$\begin{aligned} (A' - \lambda I)X' &= O \Leftrightarrow (PAP^{-1} - P\lambda IP^{-1})X' = PO \Leftrightarrow \\ &\Leftrightarrow P(AP^{-1} - \lambda IP^{-1})X' = PO \Leftrightarrow (AP^{-1} - \lambda IP^{-1})X' = O \Leftrightarrow \\ &\Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda I)P^{-1}X' = O \Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda I)P^{-1}PX = O \Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda I)X = O \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the characteristic equation as not changed with the change of coordinates, it still is $\det(A - \lambda I) = 0$. As for the eigenvectors, they remain the same, but their coordinates will now expressed with respect to the new base ■

Example 1 (*eigenvalues all real and different*). Let us consider matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -1 & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

For the characteristic equation we have

$$\begin{aligned} \det(A - \lambda I) &= \det \begin{bmatrix} 1 - \lambda & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -1 - \lambda & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix} = (1 - \lambda) \begin{vmatrix} -1 - \lambda & -1 \\ 2 & -\lambda \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} -2 & -1 - \lambda \\ 2 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = \\ &= (1 - \lambda)((-1 - \lambda)(-\lambda) + 2) + (-4 + 2(1 + \lambda)) = (1 - \lambda)((1 + \lambda)\lambda + 2) - 2 + 2\lambda = \\ &= (1 + \lambda)\lambda - \lambda((1 + \lambda)\lambda + 2) + 2\lambda = (1 + \lambda)\lambda - (1 + \lambda)\lambda^2 - 2\lambda + 2\lambda = (1 + \lambda)(1 - \lambda)\lambda \end{aligned}$$

The solution of the characteristic equation gives the eigenvalues

$$\lambda_1 = -1, \quad \lambda_2 = 0, \quad \lambda_3 = 1$$

The calculation of the corresponding eigenvectors is reported below:

$$A\bar{u}_1 = \lambda_1\bar{u}_1 \Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda_1 I)\bar{u}_1 = O \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} 2x_1 + x_3 = 0 \\ 2x_1 + 2x_2 + x_3 = 0 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} 2x_1 = -h \\ 2x_1 + 2x_2 = -h \\ x_3 = h \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = -\frac{h}{2} \\ x_2 = 0 \\ x_3 = h \end{cases} \Rightarrow \bar{u}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A\bar{u}_2 = \lambda_2\bar{u}_2 \Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda_2 I)\bar{u}_2 = O \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -1 & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 + x_3 = 0 \\ -2x_1 - x_2 - x_3 = 0 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = -h \\ x_2 = h \\ x_3 = h \end{cases} \Rightarrow \bar{u}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A\bar{u}_3 = \lambda_3\bar{u}_3 \Leftrightarrow (A - \lambda_3 I)\bar{u}_3 = O \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -2 & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x_3 = 0 \\ 2x_1 + 2x_2 - x_3 = 0 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = h \\ 2x_2 = -2h \\ x_3 = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \bar{u}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We have found:

$$\hat{u}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Then, according to PROP. 8, we can write

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -1 & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} =$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ -2 & -2 & 1 \\ -2 & -3 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

If we now consider e^{At} , by applying the result in Eq. 8, we have

$$e^{At} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -1 & -1 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} t} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ -2 & -2 & 1 \\ -2 & -3 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

This shows how diagonalization removes the exponential of a matrix in Eq. 2. This result can be generalized, as indicated in the following proposition.

PROP. 10 (*eigenvalues all real and unique*). Given a matrix A whose eigenvalues are all real and different from one another, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad e^{At} = [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \dots \quad \hat{u}_n] \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda_1} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\lambda_2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & e^{\lambda_n} \end{bmatrix} [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \dots \quad \hat{u}_n]^{-1}$$

DIM. For PROP. 2 we can write

$$e^{At} = [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \dots \quad \hat{u}_n] e^{\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_n \end{bmatrix}} [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \dots \quad \hat{u}_n]^{-1}$$

By applying PROP. 3 we have the thesis ■

Example 2 (*complex and conjugate eigenvalues*). Let us consider matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The characteristic equation is $\lambda^2 - 2\lambda + 2 = 0$ and the eigenvalues are
 $\lambda_1 = 1 + i, \quad \lambda_2 = 1 - i$

The corresponding eigenvectors are

$$\hat{u}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ i \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -i \end{bmatrix}$$

Then, according to PROP. 7 (*multiplicity*). The algebraic multiplicity of an eigenvector is always equal or greater than its geometric multiplicity.

DIM. Omitted ■

PROP. 8, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ i & -i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 0 \\ 0 & 1-i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ i & -i \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ i & -i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 0 \\ 0 & 1-i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{i}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{i}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

It is of notice that both the diagonal matrix and the eigenvectors have imaginary components in this case, but it is possible to avoid this, thanks to the following theorem.

PROP. 11 (*complex and conjugate eigenvalues*). Given the square matrix A with dimension two, if its eigenvalues are a couple of complex and conjugate values $\lambda_1 = \alpha + i\omega, \lambda_2 = \alpha - i\omega$, the corresponding eigenvectors can be written as

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \hat{u}_1 = \hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b, \quad \hat{u}_2 = \hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b$$

Moreover, the matrix can be decomposed as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_a & \hat{u}_b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_a & \hat{u}_b \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

It is then possible to show that

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad e^{At} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_a & \hat{u}_b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t \\ -e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_a & \hat{u}_b \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

DIM. If \hat{u}_1 is the eigenvector of eigenvalue $\lambda_1 = \alpha + i\omega$, we have

$$A\hat{u}_1 = \lambda_1\hat{u}_1 = \alpha\hat{u}_1 + i\omega\hat{u}_1 = \alpha(\hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b) + i\omega(\hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b) = \alpha\hat{u}_a - \omega\hat{u}_b + i(\alpha\hat{u}_b + \omega\hat{u}_a)$$

Therefore, we have found

$$A(\hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b) = (\alpha\hat{u}_a - \omega\hat{u}_b) + i(\alpha\hat{u}_b + \omega\hat{u}_a) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad \begin{cases} A\hat{u}_a = \alpha\hat{u}_a - \omega\hat{u}_b \\ A\hat{u}_b = \alpha\hat{u}_b + \omega\hat{u}_a \end{cases}$$

Now, is it true that $\hat{u}_2 = (\hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b)$? We have

$$A(\hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b) = A\hat{u}_a - iA\hat{u}_b = \alpha\hat{u}_a - \omega\hat{u}_b - i(\alpha\hat{u}_b + \omega\hat{u}_a) = (\alpha - i\omega)\hat{u}_a - (\omega + i\alpha)\hat{u}_b$$

We note now that $(\omega + i\alpha) = i\left(\frac{\omega}{i} + \alpha\right) = i\left(\frac{\omega}{i^2}i + \alpha\right) = i(-i\omega + \alpha)$. Therefore, we have

$$A(\hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b) = (\alpha - i\omega)\hat{u}_a - i(\alpha - i\omega)\hat{u}_b = (\alpha - i\omega)(\hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b) = \lambda_2(\hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b)$$

This prove Eq. 15. Then we can write:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b & \hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha + i\omega & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha - i\omega \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b & \hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

This diagonalization of A is of limited interest, because it includes complex values. We now search for a decomposition in the real field, the one in Eq. 16. First of all, we realize that from the linear independence of \hat{u}_1, \hat{u}_2 follows that \hat{u}_a, \hat{u}_b are linearly independent too:

$$(e + if)\hat{u}_1 + (g + ih)\hat{u}_2 = (0 + i0) \Leftrightarrow e = f = g = h = 0$$

↓

$$(e\hat{u}_a - f\hat{u}_b) + i(f\hat{u}_a + e\hat{u}_b) + (g\hat{u}_a + h\hat{u}_b) + i(h\hat{u}_a - g\hat{u}_b) = 0 \Leftrightarrow e = f = g = h = 0$$

↓

$$\begin{cases} (e + g)\hat{u}_a + (-f + h)\hat{u}_b = 0 \\ (f + h)\hat{u}_a + (e - g)\hat{u}_b = 0 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow e = f = g = h = 0$$

↓

$$l\hat{u}_a + m\hat{u}_b = 0 \Leftrightarrow l = m = 0$$

This means that if we introduce the matrix $P = [\hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b]$ there must exist a matrix Λ such that $\Lambda = P^{-1}AP$ (this come from PROP. 9). But what is this matrix like? We observe that

$$\hat{u}_a = P \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_b = P \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

By substitution of these expression in Eq. 17, we have

$$\begin{aligned} AP \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} &= \alpha P \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \omega P \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow P^{-1}AP \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha P^{-1}P \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \omega P^{-1}P \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \Lambda \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \omega \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ AP \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} &= \alpha P \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega P \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow P^{-1}AP \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha P^{-1}P \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega P^{-1}P \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \Lambda \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

If we now introduce the elements of Λ as unknowns, by writing

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix}$$

we have four equations:

$$\Lambda \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \omega \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \omega \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} a \\ c \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \omega \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} a \\ c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ -\omega \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Lambda \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} b \\ d \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} b \\ d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix}$$

We conclude that $\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix}$ and

$$A = P\Lambda P^{-1} = [\hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b] \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix} [\hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b]^{-1}$$

Let us consider now the exponent of A . By applying PROP. 2 and PROP. 4 we have

$$\begin{aligned} e^{At} &= e^{P\Lambda P^{-1}t} = P e^{\Lambda t} P^{-1} = P e^{\left(\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega \\ -\omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) t} P^{-1} = P e^{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \omega \\ -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix} t} P^{-1} = \\ &= P e^{\begin{bmatrix} e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t \\ -e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix} t} P^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

We find Eq. 28 ■

Example 3 (*complex and conjugate eigenvalues*). If we consider again the matrix of Example 2 and we apply the result in PROP. 11, we have the decomposition:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

By applying Eq. 17 we have

$$e^{At} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^t \cos t & e^t \sin t \\ -e^t \sin t & e^t \cos t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^t \cos t & e^t \sin t \\ -e^t \sin t & e^t \cos t \end{bmatrix}$$

Example 4 (*real and unique eigenvalues with complex and conjugate eigenvalues*). Given the square matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -2 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigenvalues and their relative eigenvectors are:

$$\lambda_1 = 1, \quad \lambda_2 = -1 + i, \quad \lambda_3 = -1 - i,$$

$$\hat{u}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} + i \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix} - i \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The results seen in this paragraph can be used to proof that the following decomposition is true:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

And that

$$e^{At} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-t} \cos t & e^{-t} \sin t \\ 0 & -e^{-t} \sin t & e^{-t} \cos t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

More generally, we have the following proposition.

PROP. 12 (*unique eigenvalues*). Given a matrix with a set of unique eigenvalues (either real or complex), we can always use the following decomposition, where we assume – for the sake of simplicity – three unique real eigenvalues ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$) and two complex and conjugate eigenvalues ($\alpha + i\omega, \alpha - i\omega$):

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad A = [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \hat{u}_3 \quad \hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b] \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha & \omega \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\omega & \alpha \end{bmatrix} [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \hat{u}_3 \quad \hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b]^{-1}$$

Where \hat{u}_i is the eigenvector of λ_i and $\hat{u}_a + i\hat{u}_b, \hat{u}_a - i\hat{u}_b$ are the eigenvector of the eigenvalues $\alpha + i\omega, \alpha - i\omega$, respectively. Moreover, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad e^{At} =$$

$$= [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \hat{u}_3 \quad \hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b] \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda_1 t} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\lambda_2 t} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\lambda_3 t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -e^{\alpha t} \sin \omega t & e^{\alpha t} \cos \omega t \end{bmatrix} [\hat{u}_1 \quad \hat{u}_2 \quad \hat{u}_3 \quad \hat{u}_a \quad \hat{u}_b]^{-1}$$

DIM. It follows from PROP. 10 and PROP. 11 ■

4 Case of eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity above one

Example 5 (real eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than one). Given the matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The characteristic equation is easily solved:

$$\begin{aligned} \det(A - \lambda I) &= \begin{vmatrix} 1 - \lambda & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 - \lambda & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow (1 - \lambda) \begin{vmatrix} 1 - \lambda & 3 \\ 0 & 2 - \lambda \end{vmatrix} &= (1 - \lambda)(1 - \lambda)(2 - \lambda) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The eigenvalues are $\lambda_1 = 1, \lambda_2 = 1, \lambda_3 = 2$. The eigenspace for the first two eigenvalues can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 - \lambda_1 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 - \lambda_1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 - \lambda_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = k \\ x_2 = 0 \\ x_3 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Therefore, it is a unidimensional space:

$$E(\lambda = 1) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} k \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} : k \in \mathbb{R} \right\}$$

For the eigenvectors of the third eigenvalue we calculate:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} 1 - \lambda_3 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 - \lambda_3 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 - \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & -1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow \begin{cases} -x_1 + x_2 + 2x_3 = 0 \\ -x_2 + 3x_3 = 0 \end{cases} &\Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = k \\ x_2 = k - 2x_3 \\ 3x_3 = k - 2x_3 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = k \\ x_2 = k - 2x_3 \\ x_3 = \frac{k}{5} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = k \\ x_2 = 3\frac{k}{5} \\ x_3 = \frac{k}{5} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the eigenspace is

$$E(\lambda = 2) = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 5k \\ 3k \\ k \end{pmatrix} : k \in \mathbb{R} \right\}$$

We see that in this case one eigenvalue has algebraic multiplicity of 2, but its geometric multiplicity is only 1, and it is not possible to find the diagonal decomposition of A . In cases like this is still possible to calculate a block diagonal decomposition, as it will be explained in the following pages.

DEF. 6 (*generalized eigenvectors*). We say that $\hat{v}^{(k)}$ is a generalized eigenvector of order k of matrix A when

$$(A - \lambda I)^k \hat{v}^{(k)} = 0, \quad (A - \lambda I)^{k-1} \hat{v}^{(k)} \neq 0$$

Therefore, the eigenvector introduced in DEF. 2 is a generalized eigenvector of order one.

PROP. 13. Given a square matrix and a eigenvalue of its, the corresponding number of generalized eigenvectors of order $k - 1$ is equal or greater than the number of generalized eigenvectors of order k . In particular, we have that given a generalized eigenvector of order k – say $\hat{v}^{(k)}$ – we always have the generalized eigenvector of order $k - 1$ given by

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \hat{v}^{(k)} = (A - \lambda I) \hat{v}^{(k+1)}$$

Note that since $\det(A - \lambda_i I) = 0$, the solution of this system – if it exists – is not unique.

DIM. If $\hat{v}^{(k)}$ is a generalized eigenvector of order k for eigenvalue λ , we have that $(A - \lambda I) \hat{v}^{(k)}$ is a generalized eigenvector of order $k - 1$:

$$(A - \lambda I)^k \hat{v}^{(k)} = 0 \Rightarrow (A - \lambda I)^{k-1} \left((A - \lambda I) \hat{v}^{(k)} \right) = 0$$

$$(A - \lambda I)^{k-1} \hat{v}^{(k)} \neq 0 \Rightarrow (A - \lambda I)^{k-2} \left((A - \lambda I) \hat{v}^{(k)} \right) \neq 0$$

So, if one generalized eigenvector of order k exists, we know that there is at least one generalized eigenvector of order $k - 1$ ■

DEF. 7 (*algorithm*). What follows is an algorithm for the determination of a set of n linearly independent generalized eigenvectors, given a square matrix A of dimension n . Given matrix A , let λ_i be one of its eigenvalues. We indicate a_i its algebraic multiplicity and g_i its geometric multiplicity. We now that it must be $g_i \leq a_i$ (PROP. 7).

1. If $g_1 < a_1$, we search for the solutions of the equations $(A - \lambda_1 I)^2 \hat{v}_1^{(2)} = 0$ with the constraint $(A - \lambda_1 I) \hat{v}_1^{(2)} \neq 0$, in other words we search for the generalized eigenvectors of the second order of λ_1 . If we obtain $a_1 - g_1$ linearly independent solutions we move on step 2, otherwise we perform the same step for the generalized eigenvectors of order three, and if it is necessary of the following orders, until we collect a total of $a_1 - g_1$ generalized eigenvectors of order ≥ 2 .
2. We repeat step 1 for $\lambda_2, \lambda_3, \dots$ (for all the remaining eigenvalues of A).

At the end of the procedure, the eigenvectors of A of all order (including order one) must be n . More precisely, let us say that the number of independent generalized eigenvectors of order j for eigenvalue λ_i is $g_i^{(j)}$, then at the end of the algorithm we must have

$$\begin{cases} g_i^{(1)} + g_i^{(2)} + \dots = a_i \\ g_i^{(1)} \geq g_i^{(2)} \geq \dots \end{cases}$$

Where $g_i^{(1)}$ is the geometric multiplicity of λ_i (also indicated simply as g_i). The second condition above is PROP. 13. It will be relevant, in what follows, to assign an order to the elements of the set of generalized eigenvector of eigenvalue λ_i , and we define this order as the one obtained by reading Table 2 row by row, from left to right. In this table it assumed that

$$\hat{v}_k^{(h)} = (A - \lambda_i I) \hat{v}_k^{(h+1)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, g_i$$

Note that the total elements in the table must be exactly a_i (the algebraic multiplicity of λ_i). Note also that each column has a number of elements different from zero that is lower than or equal to the number of significant elements of the previous column.

Order 1	Order 2	Order 3	...
$\hat{v}_1^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(3)}$...
$\hat{v}_2^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_2^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_2^{(3)}$...
$\hat{v}_3^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_3^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_3^{(3)}$...
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
$\hat{v}_{g_i}^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_{g_i}^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_{g_i}^{(3)}$...

Table 2. Generalized eigenvectors associated to the eigenvalue λ_i of geometric multiplicity g_i .

It can be proved that the n vectors obtained by this algorithm are linearly independent. We'll show in what follows that the matrix of the endomorphism F with respect to the base defined by these vectors is a block diagonal matrix (*Jordan matrix*) whose exponential has a particularly handy form (PROP. 3). The diagonal form discussed previously, for the case of eigenvalues with unitary multiplicity, is a particular case of the Jordan form.

Example 6 (*real eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than one*). Consider again matrix A of Example 5. How do we find the eigenvector of order 2 for $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 1$? We solve the system $(A - \lambda_1 I)^2 \hat{v}_1^{(2)} = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} (A - \lambda_1 I)^2 \hat{v}_1^{(2)} = 0 &\Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1-1 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1-1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2-1 \end{bmatrix}^2 \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \\ &\Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^2 \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 5 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = k \\ x_2 = h \\ x_3 = 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

This solution generates the space $L_R \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right)$. Note though that only the second vector satisfy the constraint $(A - \lambda_1 I) \hat{v}_1^{(2)} \neq 0$ (the first vector is in fact the eigenvector of the first order we found previously). Putting together the eigenvectors of all order for this matrix, we build the following set of linearly independent vectors:

$$\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{v}_1^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{v}_2^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ 3 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note $\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = (A - \lambda_1 I)\hat{v}_1^{(2)}$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 - \lambda_1 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 - \lambda_1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 - \lambda_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

And this is a general rule (proof of PROP. 13).

Example 7 (*real eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than one*). Consider matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -3 & -1 \\ 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The characteristic equation can be written $\det(A - \lambda I) = (\lambda - 2)^6$, therefore we find the eigenvalue $\lambda = 2$ with algebraic multiplicity $a = 6$. By solving the linear system $(A - 2I)X = 0$ we find the following first-order eigenvectors:

$$\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{v}_2^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{v}_3^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 4 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

We can now search for the second order eigenvectors by solving the three linear systems:

$$(A - 2I)\hat{v}_1^{(2)} = \hat{v}_1^{(1)}, \quad (A - 2I)\hat{v}_2^{(2)} = \hat{v}_2^{(1)}, \quad (A - 2I)\hat{v}_3^{(2)} = \hat{v}_3^{(1)}$$

We find a unique solution for the first two systems, no solution for the third one. In particular, we have the two second-order eigenvectors:

$$\hat{v}_1^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -4 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{v}_2^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Then we move to the third-order eigenvectors, and we solve the two linear systems:

$$(A - 2I)\hat{v}_1^{(3)} = \hat{v}_1^{(2)}, \quad (A - 2I)\hat{v}_2^{(3)} = \hat{v}_2^{(2)}$$

From the first linear system, we find one third-order eigenvector

$$\hat{v}_1^{(3)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We have now a set of 6 linearly independent generalized eigenvectors of A the fill the following table, built on the model of Table 2.

Order 1	Order 2	Order 3
$\hat{v}_1^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(3)}$
$\hat{v}_2^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_2^{(2)}$	-
$\hat{v}_3^{(3)}$	-	-

Table 3. The analogous of Table 2, for the matrix of *Example 7*.

The order of the elements of the 6 eigenvectors comes from the table itself, by reading it row by row, from left to right:

$$\hat{v}_1^{(1)}, \hat{v}_1^{(2)}, \hat{v}_1^{(3)}, \hat{v}_2^{(1)}, \hat{v}_2^{(2)}, \hat{v}_3^{(3)}$$

DEF. 8 (*Jordan canonical form*). Given a square matrix A of order n , let U be the square matrix of the same order whose columns are the vectors obtained from the algorithm in DEF. 7. Then we say that the Jordan canonical form of A is

Eq. 22 $J = U^{-1}AU$

PROP. 14. The Jordan canonical form of A is a block diagonal matrix having one squared block for each row of Table 2, for each eigenvalue of A . The generic block corresponding to eigenvalue λ_i is given by:

Eq. 23
$$\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_i & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_i & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_i & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \lambda_i \end{bmatrix}$$

The order of the block is equal the number of significant elements of the corresponding row of Table 2. Note that this proposition is true also in the case of complex eigenvalues, but it is possible to use a modified block that removes the imaginary component, as will be shown later.

DIM. The Jordan matrix can be written:

$$\begin{aligned} J &= U^{-1}(AU) = U^{-1}(A(U_1 \ U_2 \ \dots \ U_n)) = U^{-1}(AU_1 \ AU_2 \ \dots \ AU_n) = \\ &= (U^{-1}(AU_1) \ U^{-1}(AU_2) \ \dots \ U^{-1}(AU_n)) \end{aligned}$$

Where we have indicated explicitly the columns of U , represented by the generalized eigenvectors of A , by definition of Jordan canonical form. In other words, the i -th column of J can be written $J_i = U^{-1}(AU_i)$, therefore

$$UJ_i = AU_i$$

We realize then, that the elements of J_i are the coordinates with respect to the base U of vector AU_i . Let us now say that Table 2 has m significant elements in row 1 for eigenvalue λ_1 . Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} AU_1 &= A\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(1)} \\ AU_2 &= A\hat{v}_1^{(2)} = A\hat{v}_1^{(2)} - \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(2)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(2)} = (A - \lambda_1 I)\hat{v}_1^{(2)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(2)} = \hat{v}_1^{(1)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(2)} \\ AU_3 &= A\hat{v}_1^{(3)} = A\hat{v}_1^{(3)} - \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(3)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(3)} = (A - \lambda_1 I)\hat{v}_1^{(3)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(3)} = \hat{v}_1^{(2)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(3)} \\ &\dots \\ AU_m &= A\hat{v}_1^{(m)} = A\hat{v}_1^{(m)} - \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(m)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(m)} = (A - \lambda_1 I)\hat{v}_1^{(m)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(m)} = \hat{v}_1^{(m-1)} + \lambda_1\hat{v}_1^{(m)} \end{aligned}$$

Since, as said, J_i has as elements the coordinates of AU_i with respect to U , we must conclude that

$$J_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad J_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad J_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ \lambda_1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \dots \quad J_m = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \\ \lambda_1 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Repeating the same argument for the other rows of Table 2, we build all the block relative to the first eigenvalue. By repeating then the algorithm for all the eigenvalues, we have the complete Jordan canonical form ■

Example 8 (*real eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than one*). Let us consider again matrix A of Example 7. We have shown previously that matrix U , the base of generalized eigenvectors, is given by

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -4 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 4 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, the Jordan canonical form can be written

$$J = U^{-1}AU =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -4 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 4 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -3 & -1 \\ 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -4 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 4 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 4 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -3 & -1 \\ 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -4 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 4 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

Let us now try to build the Jordan canonical form by direct application of the algorithm used in the proof of PROP. 14. We know that the Jordan canonical form is a block diagonal matrix with a block for each row of Table 2, built for each of eigenvalue. In the present example, we have only one eigenvalue with algebraic multiplicity of three, therefore we expect a Jordan matrix with three blocks. The first block must have order 3, because there are three elements in the first row of Table 3. It will be given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The second block, the one corresponding to the second row of Table 3, must be of order 2, and the last one of order one. Therefore, we have the two blocks:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad [2]$$

We obtain the matrix

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} & o & o \\ o & \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} & o \\ o & o & [2] \end{bmatrix}$$

The exponential of At can then be written using PROP. 5:

$$e^{At} = e^{\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -3 & -1 \\ 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 2 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} t} = Ue^{Jt}U^{-1} = Ue^{\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} t} U^{-1} =$$

$$= Ue^{\begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} & o & o \\ o & \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} & o \\ o & o & [2] \end{bmatrix} t} U^{-1} = Ue^{\begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^{2t} & te^{2t} & t^2e^{2t} \\ 0 & e^{2t} & te^{2t} \\ 0 & 0 & e^{2t} \end{bmatrix} & o & o \\ o & o & \begin{bmatrix} e^{2t} & te^{2t} \\ 0 & e^{2t} \end{bmatrix} \\ o & o & [e^{2t}] \end{bmatrix} t} U^{-1}$$

Example 9 (*complex eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than one*). We want to consider now the case of complex eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than the geometric multiplicity. I do not find an example of such a matrix, therefore I build it, starting from the Jordan canonical form. Given

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1+i & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1-i \end{bmatrix}$$

The corresponding matrix A must have two complex conjugate eigenvalues, each of algebraic multiplicity 3. Moreover, since there is only one block for each eigenvalue, we know that the tables of the generalized eigenvalues must both have one row of three columns. In other words, each eigenvalue has three generalized eigenvectors from order one to three. We also know that the two eigenvectors of the first order must be conjugated. All that said, we choose:

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i \\ 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i \end{bmatrix}$$

Then, we derive matrix $A = UJU^{-1}$. I use Wolfram Mathematics as aid for calculations and I get:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now that we have A, let us try the inverse process up to the Jordan canonical form. I'll use Wolfram Mathematica. The characteristic polynomial of the matrix is:

$$8 - 24\lambda + 36\lambda^2 - 32\lambda^3 + 18\lambda^4 - 6\lambda^5 + \lambda^6 = 0$$

The eigenvalues are

$$\lambda_1 = 1 + i, \quad \lambda_2 = 1 - i$$

both with algebraic multiplicity three. The corresponding eigenvectors are respectively given by

$$\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{v}_2^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This can be verified by performing the products $A\hat{v}_1^{(1)}$ and $A\hat{v}_2^{(1)}$. We have:

$$A\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 2i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = (1 + i) \begin{bmatrix} 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \lambda_1 \hat{v}_1^{(1)}, \quad A\hat{v}_2^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} -2i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = (1 - i) \begin{bmatrix} 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \lambda_2 \hat{v}_2^{(1)}$$

Where we have considered that

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad \begin{cases} (1 + i)(1 + i) = 1 + 2i - 1 = 2i \\ (1 + i)(1 - i) = 1 + 1 = 2 \\ (1 - i)(1 - i) = 1 - 2i - 1 = -2i \end{cases}$$

We now move to the second-order generalized eigenvector for λ_1 and we calculate (with Wolfram Mathematica):

$$(A - \lambda_1 I) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \hat{v}_1^{(1)} \Rightarrow \hat{v}_1^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(A - \lambda_1 I) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \hat{v}_1^{(2)} \Rightarrow \hat{v}_1^{(3)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(A - \lambda_2 I) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \hat{v}_2^{(1)} \Rightarrow \hat{v}_2^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(A - \lambda_2 I) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \hat{v}_2^{(2)} \Rightarrow \hat{v}_2^{(3)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 - i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 + i \end{bmatrix}$$

We can therefore build Table 4 and we can write

$$U = [\hat{v}_1^{(1)} \quad \hat{v}_1^{(2)} \quad \hat{v}_1^{(3)} \quad \hat{v}_2^{(1)} \quad \hat{v}_2^{(2)} \quad \hat{v}_2^{(3)}] = \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i \\ 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i \end{bmatrix}$$

Which is the same matrix U we started from, to build A . The reader has now probably recognized that this decomposition of A involves complex eigenvalues and complex eigenvectors and she is already wondering if a real equivalent form is available, something equivalent to the form found for the diagonal decomposition (PROP. 11). Well, a real form does exist, be patient.

Eigenvalue	Order 1	Order 2	Order 3
$\lambda_1 = 1 + i$	$\hat{v}_1^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1+i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1-i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1+i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1-i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(3)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1+i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1-i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$
$\lambda_2 = 1 - i$	$\hat{v}_2^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1-i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1+i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\hat{v}_2^{(2)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1-i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1+i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\hat{v}_2^{(3)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1-i \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1+i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$

Table 4. Table of the generalized eigenvectors for Example 9.

To check the calculations of this example, you can copy and paste the following text in a cell of a Wolfram Mathematica Notebook:

```
U={{1+i,0,0,1-i,0,0},{0,1+i,0,0,1-i,0},{0,0,1+i,0,0,1-i},{1-i,0,0,1+i,0,0},{0,1-i,0,0,1+i,0},{0,0,1-i,0,0,1+i}};
J={{1+i,1,0,0,0,0},{0,1+i,1,0,0,0},{0,0,1+i,0,0,0},{0,0,0,1-i,1,0},{0,0,0,0,1-i,1},{0,0,0,0,0,1-i}};

V1_1={{1+i},{0},{0},{1-i},{0},{0}}
V2_1={{0},{1+i},{0},{0},{1-i},{0}}
V3_1={{0},{0},{1+i},{0},{0},{1-i}}
V1_2={{1-i},{0},{0},{1+i},{0},{0}}
V2_2={{0},{1-i},{0},{0},{1+i},{0}}
V3_2={{0},{0},{1-i},{0},{0},{1+i}}

A=U.J.Inverse[U]
```

CharacteristicPolynomial[A,λ]

V1₁={{1+i},{0},{0},{1-i},{0},{0}}

V2₁={{0},{1+i},{0},{0},{1-i},{0}}

V3₁={{0},{0},{1+i},{0},{0},{1-i}}

V1₂={{1-i},{0},{0},{1+i},{0},{0}}

V2₂={{0},{1-i},{0},{0},{1+i},{0}}

V3₂={{0},{0},{1-i},{0},{0},{1+i}}

(A-(1+i)*IdentityMatrix[6]).V2₁

(A-(1+i)*IdentityMatrix[6]).V3₁

(A-(1-i)*IdentityMatrix[6]).V2₂

(A-(1-i)*IdentityMatrix[6]).V3₂

(A-(1-i)*IdentityMatrix[6]).V3₂

PROP. 15 (*real Jordan canonical form*). Let us consider a square matrix A of order $n = 16$ whose eigenvalues are

$$\lambda_{1,1} = \alpha_1 + i\omega_1, \quad \lambda_{1,2} = \alpha_1 - i\omega_1,$$

$$\lambda_{2,1} = \alpha_2 + i\omega_2, \quad \lambda_{2,2} = \alpha_2 - i\omega_2,$$

Let us also say that $\lambda_{1,1}$ and $\lambda_{1,2}$ have algebraic multiplicity of four and geometric multiplicity of two, while $\lambda_{2,1}$ and $\lambda_{2,2}$ have algebraic multiplicity of four and geometric multiplicity of one. We therefore can build the following table, as previously shown (DEF. 7).

Eigenvalue	Order 1	Order 2	Order 3	Order 4
$\lambda_{1,1} = 1 + i$	$\hat{v}_1^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_1^{(3)}$	-
$\lambda_{1,1} = 1 + i$	$\hat{v}_2^{(1)}$	-	-	-
$\lambda_{1,2} = 1 - i$	$\overline{\hat{v}_1^{(1)}}$	$\overline{\hat{v}_1^{(2)}}$	$\overline{\hat{v}_1^{(3)}}$	-
$\lambda_{1,2} = 1 - i$	$\overline{\hat{v}_2^{(1)}}$	-	-	-
$\lambda_{2,1} = 1 + i$	$\hat{v}_3^{(1)}$	$\hat{v}_3^{(2)}$	$\hat{v}_3^{(3)}$	$\hat{v}_3^{(4)}$
$\lambda_{2,2} = 1 - i$	$\overline{\hat{v}_3^{(1)}}$	$\overline{\hat{v}_3^{(2)}}$	$\overline{\hat{v}_3^{(3)}}$	$\overline{\hat{v}_3^{(4)}}$

Then, it is possible to show that

$$A = PJP^{-1} = P \begin{bmatrix} C_1 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_1 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_2 & I & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_2 & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_2 & I \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_2 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1}$$

where

$$C_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \omega_1 \\ -\omega_1 & \alpha_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_2 & \omega_2 \\ -\omega_2 & \alpha_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad O = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

And where P is the matrix whose columns are the elements obtained by reading the following table row by row, from left to right:

	Order 1		Order 2		Order 3		Order 4	
$\lambda_{1,1}, \lambda_{1,2}$	$Re[\hat{v}_1^{(1)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_1^{(1)}]$	$Re[\hat{v}_1^{(2)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_1^{(2)}]$	$Re[\hat{v}_1^{(3)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_1^{(3)}]$	-	-
$\lambda_{1,1}, \lambda_{1,2}$	$Re[\hat{v}_2^{(1)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_2^{(1)}]$	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\lambda_{2,1}, \lambda_{2,2}$	$Re[\hat{v}_3^{(1)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_3^{(1)}]$	$Re[\hat{v}_3^{(2)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_3^{(2)}]$	$Re[\hat{v}_3^{(3)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_3^{(3)}]$	$Re[\hat{v}_3^{(4)}]$	$Im[\hat{v}_3^{(4)}]$

This matrix can easily be derived from the previous one. In general, each block of the Jordan canonical form can be written

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_i & I & O & \dots & O \\ O & C_i & I & \dots & O \\ O & O & C_i & \dots & O \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ O & O & O & \dots & C_i \end{bmatrix}$$

with $C_i = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_i & \omega_i \\ -\omega_i & \alpha_i \end{bmatrix}$ and the exponential of this block is give by Eq. 12.

DIM. Omitted, consider as a reference the proof of Theorem 3.4.1.5 of the second edition of Matrix Analysis (page 202) by R.A. Horn and C.R. Johnson ■

Example 10 (*complex eigenvalues with algebraic multiplicity greater than one*). We have found in Example 9 that $A = UJU^{-1}$ with

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad U = \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 1-i \\ 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1-i & 0 & 0 & 1+i \end{bmatrix},$$

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1+i & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1+i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1-i & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1-i \end{bmatrix}$$

According to PROP. 15 we have the real decomposition:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

This calculation can be verified by inputting into a Wolfram Mathematica Notebook the following cell:

```
U={{1,1,0,0,0,0},{0,0,1,1,0,0},{0,0,0,0,1,1},{1,-1,0,0,0,0},{0,0,1,-1,0,0},{0,0,0,0,1,-1}};
J={{1,1,1,0,0,0},{-1,1,0,1,0,0},{0,0,1,1,1,0},{0,0,-1,1,0,1},{0,0,0,0,1,1},{0,0,0,0,-1,1}};
U.J.Inverse[U]//MatrixForm
```

The structure of the decomposition is:

$$A = P \begin{bmatrix} C & I_2 & O \\ O & C & I_2 \\ O & O & C \end{bmatrix} P^{-1}$$

With

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} \operatorname{Re}(\lambda_1) & \operatorname{Im}(\lambda_1) \\ -\operatorname{Im}(\lambda_1) & \operatorname{Re}(\lambda_1) \end{bmatrix}, \quad I_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} \operatorname{Re}(\hat{v}_1^{(1)}) & \operatorname{Im}(\hat{v}_1^{(1)}) & \operatorname{Re}(\hat{v}_1^{(2)}) & \operatorname{Im}(\hat{v}_1^{(2)}) & \operatorname{Re}(\hat{v}_1^{(3)}) & \operatorname{Im}(\hat{v}_1^{(3)}) \end{bmatrix}$$

The exponential e^{At} – given PROP. 6 – can be written

$$e^{At} = P \begin{bmatrix} e^t \cos t & e^t \sin t & te^t \cos t & te^t \sin t & t^2 e^t \cos t & t^2 e^t \sin t \\ -e^t \sin t & e^t \cos t & -te^t \sin t & te^t \cos t & -t^2 e^t \sin t & t^2 e^t \cos t \\ 0 & 0 & e^t \cos t & e^t \sin t & te^t \cos t & te^t \sin t \\ 0 & 0 & -e^t \sin t & e^t \cos t & -te^t \sin t & te^t \cos t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & e^t \cos t & e^t \sin t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -e^t \sin t & e^t \cos t \end{bmatrix} P^{-1}$$

with

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

This result can be verified by using Wolfram Mathematica. We can calculate matrix $P^{-1}e^{At}P$ by using the following cell:

```
P={{1,1,0,0,0,0},{0,0,1,1,0,0},{0,0,0,0,1,1},{1,-1,0,0,0,0},{0,0,1,-1,0,0},{0,0,0,0,1,-1}};
J={{1,1,1,0,0,0},{-1,1,0,1,0,0},{0,0,1,1,1,0},{0,0,-1,1,0,1},{0,0,0,0,1,1},{0,0,0,0,-1,1}};
A=P.J.Inverse[P]
FullSimplify[TrigExpand[Inverse[P].MatrixExp[A*t].P]//MatrixForm
```

And the result is

$$\begin{bmatrix} e^t \cos[t] & e^t \sin[t] & e^t t \cos[t] & e^t t \sin[t] & \frac{1}{2} e^t t^2 \cos[t] & \frac{1}{2} e^t t^2 \sin[t] \\ -e^t \sin[t] & e^t \cos[t] & -e^t t \sin[t] & e^t t \cos[t] & -\frac{1}{2} e^t t^2 \sin[t] & \frac{1}{2} e^t t^2 \cos[t] \\ 0 & 0 & e^t \cos[t] & e^t \sin[t] & e^t t \cos[t] & e^t t \sin[t] \\ 0 & 0 & -e^t \sin[t] & e^t \cos[t] & -e^t t \sin[t] & e^t t \cos[t] \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & e^t \cos[t] & e^t \sin[t] \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -e^t \sin[t] & e^t \cos[t] \end{bmatrix}$$

As expected.